

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D7.9 - Replication video

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December, 2023 (M28) - WP7, D7.9

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450. The views expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author/s and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Technical References

Project Acronym	ePLANET
Project Title	European Public Local Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition

Deliverable No.	D7.9
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP7 - WP COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION
Lead beneficiary	LIMA
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	
Due date of deliverable	31 st December 2023
Actual submission date	2 nd January 2024

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Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
0.1	29/12/23	First proposal of deliverable	Segis VERDAGUER (LIMA)
0.2	02/01/23	Revision	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
1.0	02/01/23	Final version	Segis VERDAGUER (LIMA)

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document describes the preparation and production of the replication videos of ePLANET project.

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1 Introduction

The ePLANET project considers the development of different dissemination material, in views to increase the visibility of the project's outcomes and maximise the engagement of stakeholders and target groups within the project development.

Within this framework, a constitutional video explaining the project approach and expected impact was produced in M10. It has been used be used as key promotional material in the different social media channels of the project, as well as in presentations, conferences and public events. A set of 3 regional scaling-up videos has also been produced in M24. This scaling-up videos were tailored to the pilot regions (national language, national testimonials).

Now, a set of 2 replication videos has been produced.

Following the Grant Agreement, the ePLANET replication videos are expected to raise awareness on the opportunities of using ePLANET platform and governance strategies, and so attract public aiuthorities on the adoption of ePLANET outcomes. The expected delivery date of the deliverables is M28.

Several screenshots of the videos are included within this document. The videos will be available to be downloaded in the website of the project, as well as through the Youtube ePLANET channel at M29, following the ePLANET communication and dissemination plan.

2 Screenplay of the video

The ePLANET replication videos have been designed as a key material to highlight the added value of using ePLANET platform and governance strategies within the pilot territories, and so attract other local and regional authorities at EU level on the adoption of ePLANET outcomes.

In total, 2 replication videos have been produced, each of them focusing on different aspects and with a different format. In particular:

- Video 1: added value of the project, explained by project testimonials. It includes up to 10 short testimonials from the project consortium, describing in English the whole project in a nutshell. Total length: 3'14''.
- Video 2: focus on the platform usability. It combines a recording of the ePLANET platform while performing different tasks, with a voice-over presentation in English. Total length: 2'40''.

2.1 Video 1 - replicability by testimonials

The 3'14'' length video combines different short speeches of several members of the ePLANET consortium, following the next structure:

- A- Introduction & main interests
- B- Clustering governance
- C- ePLANET platform
- D- Stakeholders Forum
- E- Capacity Building Activities
- F- Sustainability beyond project duration

The included narration (combining the speeches of the different members of the consortium) is shown in next table:

Table 2-1 - Text structure within the video

Introduction and main interests	<p><i>ePLANET is an European funded project aiming to accelerate the energy transition in European municipalities. Following this goal, we have developed several tools, methodologies and strategies that facilitate and ease the deployment of coordinated energy transition actions by the public sector.</i></p> <p><i>ePLANET includes a proof of concept of the solutions, ensuring the correct deployment of tools in the Zlín region (in Czech Republic), Crete island (in</i></p>
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	<p>Greece) and Girona region (in Catalonia). Moreover, 6 follower regions have also joined the project.</p> <p>We want to share with you some of our key developments, to maximise their adoption by public authorities. They are very interesting to foster collaboration between public authorities and enhance the definition and deployment of energy transition plans and actions.</p>
Clustering Governance	<p>ePLANET proposes an innovative clustering governance approach based on multi-level governance, fostering dialogue and common initiatives between the different cluster members.</p> <p>Following this clustering approach, municipalities from the same or geographical territories can join efforts for common actions, sharing their knowledge and capacities, and achieving a smooth and efficient deployment of energy transition measures.</p>
ePLANET platform	<p>This clustering governance is supported by the ePLANET platform, allowing for digitalization of European Energy Action plans and related energy transition measures, data visualization and information sharing within the selected clusters and territories.</p>
Stakeholders Forum	<p>Moreover, the ePLANET Stakeholders Forum brings the knowledge of external experts to early adopters of ePLANET tools, contributing to design and tailor next steps towards maximising the usability of project developments</p>
Capacity Building Activities	<p>ePLANET has designed a user-centered Capacity Building Programme, addressing the needs identified on the pilot regions and covering a wide range of thematic areas. It includes webinars, showcases, training and workshops. Some of them are available through our website.</p>
Sustainability beyond project duration	<p>Furthermore, ePLANET has developed a repository of best practices for accelerating the progress of public authorities towards energy transition, including governance structures, funding mechanisms, capacity building strategies and technical solutions for energy transition.</p> <p>If you are interested, you can support us by signing our Joint Agreement for testing the ePLANET tools. Moreover, you can easily access most of the resources through our ePLANET website as well as through our social media and youtube channels.</p>

2.2 Video 2 - ePLANET platform

The 2'40'' length video shows some of the most interesting sections of the ePLANET platform, trying to highlight the potential of the platform as a key tool for the clustering governance and the knowledge sharing actions of the project. It follows the next structure:

- A- Sharing data amongst clusters

- B- Data visualization
- C- Digitalised SECAPs
- D- Local authority data
- E- Specific focus on energy behaviour of municipal buildings

The included speech-over narration is shown in next table:

Table 2-2 - Text structure within the video

Sharing energy data	<p><i>This is the ePLANET platform.</i></p> <p><i>The platform has several sections, tailored to specific users and allowing for a full data visualization and data sharing between specific clusters of users.</i></p>
Data visualization	<p><i>The visualization section of the platform allows you to visualize any energy parameter from different local authorities, and compare them in a friendly way. The platform allows for filtering of data, for example regarding the type of indicator or the period to visualize.</i></p> <p><i>In this case, the platform shows the total energy consumption of the municipalities, and its relative position compared to the average value from the region.</i></p>
Digitalised SECAPs	<p><i>The platform also includes a specific section for SECAP sharing. Thanks to the ePLANET harmonization and the proposed taxonomy, all the SECAPs from local and regional authorities within the region can be accessed. The information can be filtered by specific sectors and selected periods, allowing for any municipality to identify other municipalities around them that are also willing to deploy similar actions, and with potential synergies and collaborations to be exploited.</i></p> <p><i>The platform differentiates the measures for mitigation and for climate adaptation</i></p>
Local authority data	<p><i>In this section, public authorities can analyze the evolution and trends of their different indicators, in particular annual consumption from different energy sources, with all the data desglossada.</i></p> <p><i>The platform also allows for management and analysis of the deployment of their Energy Action Plan, including the modification and update of the different actions and values</i></p>
Municipal buildings	<p><i>The ePLANET platform also includes a specific section for building energy consumption analysis and data sharing. It includes a whole list of local authorities in the selected territory or cluster, together with all the buildings for each of them.</i></p>

The buildings are geo-referenced into a map, and clicking in them show the detailed information on different aspects. For each individual building, or for the whole buildings of a local authority, the platform allows -amongst other functionalities- to check the energy balance or the evolution of their energy consumption

3 Visual aspect

The next images taken from the videos show the overall approach of the graphic design in the video within its different sections.

Figure 3-1 -Video screenshots: testimonials-based video

4 Online repository

The 3 scaling-up videos have been uploaded in the ePLANET Youtube channel, and will be also accessible via the ePLANET website. The communication and dissemination actions planned for next months will also include the dissemination of those videos through the different channels (LinkedIn, news, twitter, workshops, webinars, etc).

Direct link: www.youtube.com/@ePLANETproject173

